

Antibody Characterization Report for **STING1 (UniProt ID: Q86WV6)** YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Short protein name used in this report: STING1

Recommended protein name: Stimulator of interferon genes protein

Alternative protein names: Endoplasmic reticulum interferon stimulator (ERIS), Mediator of IRF3 activation (hMITA), Transmembrane protein 173

Gene name: *STING1*

Uniprot: Q86WV6

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized sixteen STING1 commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol [2, 3] based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. We identified many well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. A THP-1 *STING1* KO line is available at Abcam and was used in this study. THP-1 was selected based on evidence of appropriate STING1 protein expression determined through DepMap [4, 5].

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab271147	CVCL_0006	THP-1	WT
Abcam	ab270493	CVCL_B1AK	THP-1	<i>STING1</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the STING1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab181125**	1000056-10	AB_2916053	recombinant-mono	EPR13130	rabbit	0.30	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab227704**	1004954-2	AB_3083474	recombinant-mono	SP338	rabbit	1.50	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab227705**	1062328-1	AB_3076486	recombinant-mono	SP339	rabbit	0.31	Wb
Abcam	ab239074**	1001652-16	AB_3068528	recombinant-mono	EPR13130-55	rabbit	0.53	Wb, IP, IF
ABclonal	A21051**	6100001330	AB_3083450	recombinant-mono	ARC57967	rabbit	0.29	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	13647**	9	AB_2732796	recombinant-mono	D2P2F	rabbit	0.06	Wb, IP
Cell Signaling Technology	50494**	8	AB_2799375	recombinant-mono	D1V5L	rabbit	0.56	Wb, IP
Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank	CPTC-STING1-1**	4/27/23-15ug/mL	AB_3068346	recombinant-mono	CPTC-STING1-1	rabbit	0.02	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX134373	43628	AB_2887262	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.42	Wb, IF
Novus Biologicals (Bio-Techne)	NBP2-24683	G-4	AB_2868483	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Novus Biologicals (Bio-Techne)	NBP3-18816**	COMU01	AB_3068548	recombinant-mono	2922D	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Proteintech	19851-1-AP	00118975	AB_10665370	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.70	Wb, IP, IF
R&D Systems (Bio-Techne)	MAB7169*	CFWR0420041	AB_10971940	monoclonal	723505	mouse	0.20	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	702993**	2842286	AB_2762404	recombinant-mono	2H1L5	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-26030*	YJ4087701	AB_2725437	monoclonal	OTI4H1	mouse	1.00	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-32768**	YJ4089249A	AB_2810045	recombinant-mono	JM03-47	rabbit	1.00	Wb

Wb=western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All the STING1 antibodies tested are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A-21429 and A-21424).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 (ATCC modification) (Gibco, cat. number A1049101) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 0.05 mM 2-Mercaptoethanol (Gibco, cat. number 21985023, 2 mM L-glutamine (Wisent cat. number 609-065), 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201).

THP-1 WT and *STING1* KO cells (listed in Table 1) were treated with 200 ng/ml of phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) (Abcam, cat. number ab147465) for 2 days. 200 ng/ml of PMA was added to fresh medium in both day 1 and day 2 [6].

Antibody screening by western blot

Western blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [3]. PMA-treated THP-1 WT and *STING1* KO cells (listed in Table 1) were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from

Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [3]. Antibody-beads conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg of antibody (with an exception 20 µl of antibody CPTC-STING1-1** and 20 µl of antibody 13647**) to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

PMA-treated THP-1 WT cells were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels. Prot-A:HRP (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8651) was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 2.0 µg/ml.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Immunofluorescence was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [3]. PMA-treated THP-1 WT and *STING1* KO cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively. The fluorescent dyes used are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number C2925 and C34565). WT and KO cells were plated in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator. Cells were fixed in 4% PFA (in PBS) for 15 min at room temperature and then washed 3 times with PBS. Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5%

BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary STING1 antibodies O/N at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification. Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Figure 1: STING1 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: STING1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (1/2)

Figure 2: STING1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (2/2)

Figure 3: STING1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Figure 1: STING1 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of THP-1 WT and *STING1* KO treated with PMA were prepared, and 40 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated STING1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: ab181125** at 1/1000, ab227704** at 1/200, ab227705** at 1/1000, ab239074** at 1/1000, A21051** at 1/1000, 13647** at 1/1000, 50494** at 1/1000, CPTC-STING1-1** at 1/10, GTX134373 at 1/1000, NBP2-24683 at 1/1000, NBP3-18816** at 1/1000, 19851-1-AP at 1/1000, MAB7169* at 1/1000, 702993** at 1/1000, MA5-26030* at 1/1000, MA5-32768** at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 42 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 2: STING1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

PMA-treated THP-1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated STING1 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the indicated STING1 antibody. For western blot, NBP3-18816** was used at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate; HC=antibody heavy chain. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 3: STING1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

PMA-treated THP-1 WT and *STING1* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. Cells were stained with the indicated STING1 antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (identification of WT cells), red (antibody staining) and far-red (identification of KO cells) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. Antibody dilution used: ab181125** at 1/300, ab227704** at 1/1000, ab227705** at 1/300, ab239074** at 1/500, A21051** at 1/300, 13647** at 1/60, 50494** at 1/500, CPTC-STING1-1** at 1/20, GTX134373 at 1/1000, NBP2-24683 at 1/1000, NBP3-18816** at 1/1000, 19851-1-AP at 1/200, MAB7169* at 1/700, 702993** at 1/250, MA5-26030* at 1/1000, MA5-32768** at 1/1000. Bars = 10 µm. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

References

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